

FAMILY LILIACEAE JUSS. OF ALTAI MOUNTAIN COUNTRY

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Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

The data set contains an up-to-date list of representatives of the family Liliaceae Juss. of Altai Mountain Country (<http://altaiflora.asu.ru>). The data set is intended to provide all interested users of GBIF with information on the distribution of the family Liliaceae Juss. within the AMC, identifying the locations of storage of material in world collections and other types of analyzes (taxonomic, phenological, etc.) using the available data sets in GBIF.

Geographic scope

Altai Mountainous Country (Russia, Kazakhstan, China and Mongolia)

Bibliography

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GBIF registration

Registration date October 3, 2022
Metadata last modified February 20, 2023
Publication date February 20, 2023

Hosted by Altai State University
Installation altb.asu.ru/ipt
Installation contacts Alexey Vaganov

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Endpoints <http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/archive.do?r=liliaceae> (Darwin Core Archive) <http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/eml.do?r=liliaceae> (EML)
Preferred identifier DOI10.15468/m94dd2
Alternative identifiers <http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/resource?r=liliaceae>

Citation

Vaganov A, Zholnerova E (2023). Family Liliaceae Juss. of Altai Mountain Country. Version 1.6. Altai State University. Checklist dataset
<https://doi.org/10.15468/m94dd2> accessed via GBIF.org on 2023-10-06.

The research was carried out within the state assignment of Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation (theme No. FZMW-2023-0008).